

Deep Reinforcement Learning-Based Slice-aware Caching for Integrated TN/NTN 6G Networks

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Abstract—The sixth generation (6G) of mobile networks seeks to leverage Integrated Terrestrial and Non-Terrestrial Networks (ITNTN) to support next-generation applications. However, despite increased network densification, meeting the stringent latency requirements—particularly for delay-sensitive applications—remains a significant challenge due to the high latency overhead introduced by non-terrestrial nodes. Content caching offers a potential solution to reduce content access delays and backhaul bandwidth costs by pre-storing content closer to the end users. However, the heterogeneity of nodes, the varying content popularity and the distinct Quality of Service (QoS) requirements introduced by network slicing complicate caching decisions in ITNTNs. For instance, prioritizing content related to critical services (e.g., emergency services) over popular content (e.g., social media files) may better address QoS needs, albeit with lower hit ratios, an aspect not explored in existing works. This paper introduces SaCCA-RL (Reinforcement Learning-based Slice-aware Content Caching Algorithm) for selecting which content to cache and its placement under constrained ITNTN node capacities, considering different and varying content popularity and priority. Simulations show that SaCCA-RL results in more than 10% improvement in terms of cache gain compared to baseline algorithms, while guaranteeing 100% hit-ratio for critical content.

Index Terms—6G, Content caching, Network slicing, Reinforcement learning, Satellite network

I. INTRODUCTION

Sixth-generation (6G) technology aims to enable seamless, anytime-anywhere connectivity—essential for supporting emerging services—through the Integration of Terrestrial and Non-Terrestrial Networks (ITNTN) [1]. In this way, non-terrestrial nodes (NTNs) such as satellites will be equipped with compute and storage capabilities to supplement the terrestrial nodes.

Despite the increased network densification under ITNTN, meeting the latency demands of delay-sensitive services (e.g., collision detection) remains a challenge [2] due to the large propagation delay of NTNs. Content caching has been proposed to address this issue by pre-storing frequently accessed content (e.g. libraries and/or databases for task execution) on various nodes for future retrieval by requesting users. This approach eliminates repeated content transmissions from the cloud to individual users, thereby reducing latency and alleviating backhaul traffic [3]. This reduces delay and eases backhaul traffic by avoiding repeated cloud transmissions [4].

However, content caching in ITNTN poses unique challenges due to node heterogeneity in computational capabilities, delay performance, coverage overlap, and variations in content popularity across different network layers. Prior studies

have addressed the cache placement problem in stand-alone terrestrial networks [5]–[7], UAV-assisted vehicular networks [3], [8]–[11], and ITNTN scenarios [2], [4], [9]–[14]. These approaches typically determine what content to cache and where to place it based on content popularity, with the primary objective of maximizing the cache hit ratio by favoring highly popular content. For instance, [4] proposes a weighted caching strategy for LEO satellites using regional content popularity to pre-store frequently requested files, while [8] employs an LSTM model and reinforcement learning to predict and pre-cache popular content in Internet-of-Vehicles. Similarly, [6] formulates the caching problem as a multi-objective optimization problem, using gated recurrent units to predict time-varying popularity of content. In [2], caching for airborne users in ITNTN is modeled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), with decisions driven by content popularity under latency constraints.

Nevertheless, existing content caching strategies overlook service criticality, a key consideration introduced by network slicing in 5G and beyond. Network slicing distinguishes services by their Quality of Service (QoS) requirements. For instance, ultra-reliable low latency communications (uRLLC) and enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMMB), among others, with critical slices services (e.g., collision avoidance) demanding stricter latency guarantees and incurring higher penalties for violations. Prioritizing content (e.g. analytics models or libraries) related to critical service execution over purely popular content (e.g. social media files) introduces a novel trade-off between popularity and priority, an important research dimension that remains underexplored. This trade-off complicates the caching problem, as content popularity and criticality do not always align, and user request patterns across slices is dynamic with location and time.

To address this gap, we propose a slice-aware content caching algorithm for ITNTN that jointly considers content popularity and service criticality/priority (based on supported service class or slices), enabling more intelligent and QoS-aligned cache decisions. Unlike prior work, the proposed approach accounts for the dynamic nature of content popularity and user requests across service groups at the different ITNTN nodes and locations. Our contribution is threefold:

- 1) We formulate a content caching problem in ITNTN that integrates content priority (service criticality) and popularity.
- 2) We introduce SaCCA-RL, a Reinforcement Learning-

based Slice-aware Content Caching Algorithm, to maximize caching benefits.

- 3) We extensively evaluate SaCCA-RL performance against five benchmark algorithms, using multiple performance metrics.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the system model, Section III introduces the SaCCA-RL algorithm, Section IV discusses the performance evaluation, and Section V concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM DEFINITION

This section introduces the system model and the problem definition. The notations adopted are given in Table I.

Fig. 1. System Model

A. Network topology

The substrate network is modeled as a graph $G = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{L})$ where $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{N}_G \cup \mathcal{N}_S$ and \mathcal{L} denote a set of substrate nodes and links, respectively. The set \mathcal{N}_G consists of terrestrial base stations (TBS) set $\mathcal{B} = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_B\}$ and a remote cloud denoted by a unit set $\mathcal{C} = \{0\}$. The set \mathcal{N}_S consists of non-terrestrial base stations (NTBS) denoted by a set $\mathcal{N}_S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_S\}$ ¹. Each node $h \in \mathcal{N}$ is characterized by a caching capacity cap_h , which is limited except for $h \in \mathcal{C}$.

As shown in Fig. 1, each NTBS covers multiple terrestrial regions (i.e., area covered by one TBS). These regions are denoted by $\mathcal{R} = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_R\}$. At a given time t , each region is assumed to be covered by at least one NTBS. Specifically, $\gamma_{r,j}^t = 1$ indicates that region r is within coverage area of NTBS j , and $\gamma_{r,j}^t = 0$ otherwise. Each user is capable of directly connecting to both the TBS and the NTBS within their coverage region. We define α_{NT}^r as the fraction of users in region r associated with the NTBS, with $1 - \alpha_{NT}^r$ representing users associated to regional TBS. The binary variable $x_{h,u}^{r,t} \in \{0, 1\}$ is defined as to 1 if user $u \in \mathcal{U}$ in region r is associated with node $h \in \mathcal{B} \cup \mathcal{S}$ at time t , and 0 otherwise.

B. Request model

Let $\mathcal{U} = \{1, 2, \dots, U\}$ represent the set of all users each of whom requests content from a set $\mathcal{F} = \{1, 2, \dots, F\}$. Users belong to different service groups/slices by based on the

¹The terms "non-terrestrial" and "satellite" are used interchangeably.

content they request. Based on the supported service group, $\beta_{f,r}^t$ denotes the priority associated with content $f \in \mathcal{F}$ in region r at $t \in T$. In addition, c_f denotes the size of $f \in \mathcal{F}$.

1) *Content popularity model*: Content popularity is region-dependent, influenced by factors such as culture and social status. For instance, collision avoidance detection content is more popular in urban areas compared to remote ones. Content popularity follows Zipf's law [6], where the F files are sorted in descending order of popularity, with the popularity rank of the k^{th} file expressed as

$$\rho_f^k = \frac{(R_f + q)^{-\alpha}}{\sum_{k \in F} (R_k + q)^{-\alpha}}, \quad (1)$$

where $R_f \in \{1, 2, \dots, F\}$ is the rank of content f in descending order. The parameters α and q denote the skewness factor and the plateau factor respectively.

C. Channel modeling

Users can access content cached at both TBS and line-of-sight NTBS nodes. Each TBS associated users are operating on a fixed, interference-free channel under the Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) scheme. The downlink transmission rate between user $u \in \mathcal{U}$ and TBS $b \in \mathcal{B}$ is given by [15]

$$R_{b,u} = W_{b,u} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P_{b,u} \gamma_{b,u}}{\sigma^2} \right). \quad (2)$$

The user allocated bandwidth $W_{b,u}$ by TBS b is $W_{b,u} = \frac{W_b}{|\mathcal{N}_b|}$, where W_b is the total bandwidth and $|\mathcal{N}_b|$ is the number of users associated to TBS b . The parameters $P_{b,u}$ and $\gamma_{b,u}$ denote the transmit power and channel gain between user u and TBS b , respectively.

For NTBS-associated users, the transmission rate between a user u and a satellite node s is modeled as

$$R_{s,u} = W_{s,u} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P_{s,u} g_{u,s}}{\sigma^2} \right), \quad (3)$$

where $W_{s,u}$, $P_{s,u}$, $g_{u,s}$, σ^2 denote the channel bandwidth, satellite transmit power, the channel gain, and the noise power, respectively. Assuming free-space path loss model [15],

$$g_{u,s} = G_a \left(\frac{c}{4\pi f_c dist_{u,s}} \right)^\eta, \quad (4)$$

where G_a , η , $dist_{u,s}$, f_c , c denote the antenna gain, the path loss exponent, distance between user u and the satellite s , transmission frequency and speed of light, respectively. Fixed transmission rates $R_{t,b}$, $R_{t,s}$ and $R_{t,h,c}$ are assumed for inter-TBS, inter-NTBS, and node h -cloud links [15].

D. Delay modeling

We focus on the propagation delay for content access, as it is the one most affected by the caching strategy. However, this approach can be extended to other delay types. To enable cache content sharing among neighboring nodes, we define a variable $h_{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}$, where $h_{i,j} = 1$ if node i is a neighbour of node j , and 0 otherwise. The neighbor probability $p_{i,j} \in [0, 1]$

represents the likelihood of $h_{i,j} = 1$. Node i is considered a neighbor of j if content requested by users at j , not cached locally, can be retrieved from i before resorting to the cloud.

For NTBS-associated users, if the requested content is cached in the NTBS, it is delivered with a single-hop delay $d_{u,s} = c_f/R_{s,u}$. Otherwise, the content is fetched from a neighboring TBS, resulting in a delay $d_{u,s} = c_f/R_{s,u} + c_f/R_{s,b}$. If unavailable at the TBS, the content is retrieved from the cloud, incurring in a delay $d_{u,s} = c_f/R_{s,c}$, dominated by the satellite-to-cloud transmission.

For TBS-associated users, if the requested content is cached at the TBS, it is delivered with a delay $d_{u,b} = c_f/R_{b,u}$. Otherwise, it is retrieved from a neighboring NTBS, adding a delay $d_{u,b} = c_f/R_{b,u} + c_f/R_{s,b}$. If unavailable at NTBS, the neighbor TBS cache is checked, adding a delay $d_{u,b} = \frac{c_f}{R_{b,u}} + \frac{c_f}{R_{b,b}}$. If all fail, the content is fetched from the cloud with delay $d_{u,b} = \frac{c_f}{R_{b,c}}$ dominated by TBS-to-cloud delay.

E. Problem formulation

In a multi-layer network with varying content popularity and priority, and nodes with limited caching capacity, the caching problem involves determining: 1) *which files to cache*, and 2) *where to place them*. The aim is to reduce access latency by storing relevant content closer to users instead of fetching it from the cloud. Let $\chi_{f,h}^t \in \{0,1\}$ represent whether $f \in \mathcal{F}$ is cached at node $h \in \mathcal{N}$ at time $t \in \mathcal{T}$. Similarly, let $y_{u,f}^t \in \{0,1\}$ be 1 if user $u \in \mathcal{U}$ requests content f at time t , and 0 otherwise. When $\chi_{f,h}^t = 0 \forall h \in \mathcal{B} \cup \mathcal{S}$, the user fetches the file from the cloud with delay denoted by $d_{u,f,c}^t$, otherwise, the file is fetched from the caching node h with delay $d_{u,f,h}^t$ where $d_{u,f,h}^t \ll d_{u,f,c}^t$.

We model the caching gain as the delay reduction achieved by caching a file. For user $u \in \mathcal{U}$ the gain is calculated as the difference in delay between fetching from the cloud and from the cache, evaluated as

$$g_{u,f}^t = y_{u,f}^t \chi_{f,h}^t [d_{u,f,c}^t - d_{u,f,h}^t]. \quad (5)$$

Note that $g_{u,f}^t = 0$ when $\chi_{f,h}^t = 0 \forall h \in \mathcal{B} \cup \mathcal{S}$. Considering all users in the system, the cachable file set \mathcal{F} and all possible caching node set $h \in \mathcal{N}$, the optimisation problem is formulated to maximize the caching benefit for each time window $t \in \mathcal{T}$ obtained by each user on average across all regions, formulated as

$$\text{maximize} : \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \frac{1}{|\mathcal{U}|} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \beta_{f,t}^r g_{u,f}^t \quad (6)$$

s.t

$$C.1 \quad \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \chi_{f,h}^t c_f \leq Cap_h \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{N}, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (7)$$

$$C.2 \quad \sum_{h \in \mathcal{N}} x_{h,u}^{r,t} = 1 \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, t \in \mathcal{T}, r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (8)$$

$$C.3 \quad \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \beta_{f,r}^t = 1 \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R}, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (9)$$

where $\beta_{f,r}^t$ is the priority of f in region r at $t \in \mathcal{T}$. C.1, C.2 enforce cache capacity and user association constraints, while

C.3 ensures the total file priority in a region sums to one.

Overall, from Eq. (6), caching content with higher priority provides greater benefits, which is an important, practical consideration to mitigate QoS violation for critical services. Moreover, to maximize the average gain per user, it is advantageous to cache content that is highly popular. However, high priority content does not always align with popular content, which complicates the solution to the formulated problem.

TABLE I
NOTATION

Parameter	Description
\mathcal{F}	A set of all content files
$\chi_{f,h}^t \in \{0,1\}$	$\chi_{f,h}^t = 1$ if $f \in \mathcal{F}$ is cached at $h \in \mathcal{N}$ at $t \in \mathcal{T}$
$y_{u,f}^t \in \{0,1\}$	$y_{u,f}^t \in \{0,1\} = 1$ if $f \in \mathcal{F}$ is requested by user $u \in \mathcal{U}$ at $t \in \mathcal{T}$
$h_{i,j} \in \{0,1\}$	$h_{i,j} = 1$ if node $i \in \mathcal{N}$ is a neighbor to $j \in \mathcal{N}$
cap_h	Cache capacity of node $h \in \mathcal{N}$
$R_{t,b,b}$	Transmission rate between TBSs
$R_{t,b,s}$	Transmission rate between TBS and Sat
$R_{t,b,u}$	Transmission rate between user and TBS
$R_{t,s,u}$	Transmission rate between user and the Sat
$R_{t,b,c}$	Transmission rate between TBS and cloud
α_{NT}	Fraction of users linked to the NTBS in region r
$\eta_{r,j}^t \in \{0,1\}$	$\eta_{r,j}^t = 1$ if region $r \in \mathcal{R}$ is under coverage of sat $j \in \mathcal{S}$ at $t \in \mathcal{T}$
$x_{h,u}^{r,t} \in \{0,1\}$	$x_{h,u}^{r,t} = 1$ if $u \in \mathcal{U}$ is associated to node $h \in \mathcal{N}$ at t
$z_{f,u}^t \in \{0,1\}$	$z_{f,u}^t = 1$ if f is requested by user $u \in \mathcal{U}$ at $t \in \mathcal{T}$
$\rho_{r,f}^t$	Popularity of file $f \in \mathcal{F}$ in $r \in \mathcal{R}$ at $t \in \mathcal{T}$.

III. REINFORCEMENT LEARNING-BASED SLICE-AWARE CONTENT CACHING ALGORITHM (SACCA-RL)

Solving the Integer Linear Programming (ILP) problem formulated in Eq. (6) to determine the optimal caching strategy involves evaluating a vast number of content-hosting combinations, making it computationally intensive especially in ITNTN scenarios characterized by many nodes. As exact solvers like CPLEX are unsuitable for delay-sensitive scenarios, this paper introduces SaCCA-RL (**RL-based Slice-aware Content Caching Algorithm**) which efficiently approximates near-optimal solutions within practical time of evaluation. The algorithm and its MDP framework are detailed below.

A. MDP model

We model the system as a fully observable environment for the RL agent, represented as an MDP defined by the tuple (S_t, A_t, P_t, R_t) , where S_t, A_t, P_t, R_t denote the system state at time t , set of all possible actions related to the caching decision, state transition probabilities and the obtained reward for each state transition, respectively. The MDP tuple parameters for our scenario are discussed below.

1) *State space*: The system state includes key features from both the multi-layer infrastructure (e.g., caching capacity) and content (e.g., priority, popularity, cache status) to help the agent infer actions for maximizing long-term rewards. For each content $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and host node $h \in \mathcal{N}$, we define a feature vector $A_{h,f}^t$ as $A_{h,f}^t = \{a_{1,f}^t, a_{2,f}^t, \dots, a_{|\mathcal{N}|,f}^t\}$, where $a_{h,f}^t$ is a vector of features relating f and node h . Each $a_{h,f}^t$

captures the popularity of f at h for both associated users and neighbor nodes, the caching status $\chi_{f,h}^t$, cache capacity Cap_h and priority of f . The global state is constructed by concatenating these vectors for all $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and $h \in \mathcal{N}$.

2) *Action space*: For each NTBS, the agent selects both a content file to cache and its placement in discrete steps until all caching space in the satellite coverage is examined. To jointly perform caching decision of a content and its placement, the action space at each step is modeled as a vector

$$A(t) = \{0, \chi_{1,1}^t, \dots, \chi_{1,F}^t, \chi_{2,1}^t, \dots, \chi_{2,F}^t, \chi_{N,1}^t, \dots, \chi_{N,F}^t\}. \quad (10)$$

3) *Reward*: The reward signal is aligned with the deployment objective given in Eq. (6), formulated as

$$\text{reward} = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \beta_{f,r} \rho_{r,f}^t (g_{u,f}^t / \hat{g}_{u,f}^t), \quad (11)$$

where the normalization term $\hat{g}_{u,f}^t$ is the gain obtained if f was cached at the local node of the associated user.

B. Architecture and training of the policy neural network

The policy neural network for SaCCA-RL consists of four main layers: 1) the input layer, which receives as input the state feature matrix; 2) a convolutional layer, which performs a convolution between the input feature matrix and the internal weights of the layer; 3) a softmax layer, which transforms the convolutional layer output into a vector of probabilities, reflecting the suitability of each action; 4) filtering layer which ensures only valid actions are considered.

During the training phase, the policy network outputs probability distribution over the available actions. For each satellite coverage region, the agent selects actions in discrete steps until all the cache space is examined. At each decision step, actions with the highest probability are typically chosen, however, during training, a balance between exploration and exploitation is maintained due to the random initialization of neural network parameters. After completing a decision sequence, a reward is computed using Eq. (11) and is used to update the neural network's internal weights through backpropagation. Gradients resulting from different decision sequences are stored in a buffer and applied together to update the neural network's internal weights once a batch size is reached. This batch processing approach, compared to updating after each sequence, ensures faster and more stable training. The training stage results are shown in Fig. 2.

From Fig. 2(a), the average reward per epoch obtained by the policy network increases with training epochs, indicating its ability to learn optimal decisions in dynamic conditions. Similarly, Figs. 2(b) and 2(c) show gains in content diversity (the fraction of content type that are cached at the local or neighbour nodes to the total number of requested content types) and a reduction in average content access delay, respectively with training epochs.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section includes the simulation setup and the discussion of obtained results.

A. Simulation setup

We consider that each NTBS covers 5 TBS (regions) and 6 content types, with the content priorities being drawn from a uniform distribution. User distances to the NTBS are set at 1000 km, and inter-satellite link delays are fixed at 40 ms. Each region has 500 total requests, with a fraction α_{NT} of these linked to the satellite and the rest to the TBS. The rest simulation parameters are listed in Table. II.

TABLE II
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value	Description
$ \mathcal{S} $	2	No. of NTBS nodes
$ \mathcal{B} _r$	5	Number of TBS per region
$R_{t,b}$	5 MB/s	Data rate between TBSs
$R_{t,c}$	1 MB/s	Data rate between cloud and TBS
$R_{c,s}$	1 MB/s	Data rate between cloud and NTBS
C_f	20 MB	Content size
α	0.8	Skewness factor
q	0	Plateau factor
C_B and C_S	U(50,100) MB	TBS and NTBS capacity
W_s, W_b	2.4, 0.5 MHz	NTBS and TBS bandwidth
G_a, η	4.11, 2.8	Antenna gain and Pathloss exponent
γ_b	10 W	TBS transmission power
P_s	43 dbm	NTBS transmission power
f_c	2800 MHz	Carrier frequency
σ^2	10^{-9} W	Noise power

B. Benchmark algorithms

To evaluate the performance of SaCCA-RL, several benchmark algorithms were considered. These include:

1) *Global Popularity algorithm (Pop-Global)*: Sorts the regional content files by their popularity. Starting with the NTBS, the files are cached according to their popularity until the cache is exhausted.

2) *Local Popularity algorithm (Pop-Local)*: Ranks the files by their popularity at each host node (either TBS or NTBS). Then, files are selected according to their popularity until the cache is fully utilized.

3) *Global Priority (Priot-Global)*: Prioritizes content based on regional importance and caches files in descending priority order, beginning with the NTBS until the regional cache is fully utilized.

4) *Local Priority (Priot-Local)*: Uses node-specific content priorities (either TBS or NTBS) to select files for caching in a descending priority order until cache space is fully utilized.

5) *Random (Random)*: Randomly selects the files to cache at each host node to fill the available host cache space.

C. Performance Metrics

The algorithms are evaluated based on three key metrics: **cache gain** (delay reduction for a service, weighted by its priority as introduced in Eq. (5)), **total hit ratio** (the proportion of user requests served by cached content) and **content diversity** (the fraction of requested content types available in local or neighboring node caches).

Fig. 2. Results of training step of the policy neural network

Fig. 3. Effect of Neighborhood Probability

1) *Impact of neighborhood probability:* As shown in Fig. 3, increasing neighborhood probability between nodes enhances caching gain, total hit ratio and content diversity, thanks to shared cached content among neighbors when local caches lack the requested content. In Fig. 3(a), *SaCCA-RL* achieves 13% improvement in cache gain with an average value of 0.37 followed by *Pop-local* and *Pop-global* (both with 0.32) and *Priot-global* (0.31). *Priot-local* and *Random* achieve the worst performance with an average value of 0.29 and 0.28 respectively. *SaCCA-RL*'s strength lies in its intelligent trade-off between content popularity and priority. Moreover, from Fig. 3(b) *SaCCA-RL* remains competitive within (0.6% margin in terms of total hit ratio) with an average hit ratio value of 72.2% compared to *Pop-global* and *Pop-local* whose average total hit ratio values are 72.2% and 72.0% respectively. *Pop-local* greedily caches content based on local popularity resulting in high hit ratio at local nodes but such content may not be reusable by the neighbors. On the contrary, *SaCCA-RL* reduces content duplication across neighbors to improve global cache utility. From Fig. 3(c), *SaCCA-RL* advantage in content diversity, reaching an average of 0.68 (implying that 68% of the requested content types are always cached at the local or neighboring node), outperforming *Pop-global* and *Priot-global* (both at 0.67), and significantly surpassing *Random* and *Pop-local* (both at 0.62) and *Priot-Local* (0.53).

2) *Impact of Skewness parameter:* The skewness parameter α of the Zipf distribution determines the concentration of content request probabilities, with low α values resulting in a nearly uniform distribution and high α values causing a

skewed distribution dominated by top-ranked content. The effects of α on various algorithms is analyzed in Fig. 4. As α increases, popularity-based models, especially *Pop-local*, achieve significant performance gains due to greater variance in content requests. In contrast, priority and random algorithms remain unaffected as they do not take content popularity in their decisions. On the other hand, *SaCCA-RL*, by jointly optimizing for popularity and priority, maintains superior performance across different distributions of content popularity.

3) *Impact of service criticality:* In Fig. 5, the impact of service criticality is analyzed for five service types by varying one content type's priority from 0.2 to 0.9, with the others sharing equal priority from the remainder. From Fig. 5(a), *SaCCA-RL* outperforms all baselines with a cache gain of 0.04 (a 12% improvement over the best-performing baseline, *Pop-global* at 0.03), followed by *Priot-global* (0.029), *Pop-local* and *Priot-local* (both at 0.027), and *Random* (0.022). Fig. 5(b) reveals that *SaCCA-RL* hit ratio declines with increase in critical content priority, reflecting its shift toward prioritizing critical services over general popularity. *Priot-local* has the lowest hit ratio as it greedily caches critical content, but it achieves a high cache gain for high priority values of critical content. In terms of critical content hit ratio in Fig. 5(c), the priority based algorithms *Priot-local* and *Priot-global* result in 100% hit ratio for the critical content, since these greedily cache content based on priority irrespective of their popularity. However, *SaCCA-RL* demonstrates a strong adaptive capability by progressively increasing the hit ratio for critical content as its assigned priority rises—ultimately achieving a 100% hit ratio when

Fig. 4. Effect of skewness parameter

Fig. 5. Effect of Critical content priority

the priority nears 1. This behavior highlights the algorithm’s ability to dynamically adjust to deal with content importance and popularity aspects without requiring retraining.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper addresses the problem of content caching in storage capacity constrained ITNTN networks, focusing on a multi-slice scenario with different content popularity and priority levels. To tackle the complexity of the underlying ILP problem, we proposed *SaCCA-RL*, a policy gradient based reinforcement learning algorithm designed to derive efficient caching decisions in dynamic settings. Simulation results show that *SaCCA-RL* achieves up to 13% improvement in cache gain, while maintaining a competitive total hit ratio—within a 0.6% margin of the best-performing baseline methods. Moreover, *SaCCA-RL* intelligently deals with the trade-off between content popularity and priority levels resulting in 100% hit-ratio for critical slice related content. These results confirm that *SaCCA-RL* is well-suited for multi-slice scenarios characterized by spatio-temporal popularity variations in content demand.

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